

THE IMPACT OF PLAYING MOBILE LEGENDS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS OF JUNIOR AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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The Impact of Playing Mobile Legends on Academic Performance in Mathematics of Junior and Senior High School Students

Jan Angelo G. Morata,* Kelvin Carl D. Fulay
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of Mobile Legends gameplay on academic performance in Mathematics among junior and senior high school students. A linear regression model was employed to analyze the impact between specific gaming variables—Gameplay Experience Duration, Gaming Time, Gaming Schedule, Weekly Gaming Frequency, and Matches per Session—and students' Mathematics grades. Using a sample of 101 respondents, the regression model yielded an R^2 value of 0.051 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.002, indicating that the gaming variables collectively explained only 5.1% of the variance in Mathematics grades, with minimal improvement after adjustment. The overall model was not statistically significant ($F = 1.031$, $p = 0.404$). Individually, all gaming variables had p -values above the 0.05 threshold, confirming no statistically significant impacts. The standardized beta coefficients (β) ranged from negligible positive to negative values: Gameplay Experience Duration ($\beta = 0.213$, $p = 0.219$), Gaming Time ($\beta = -0.119$, $p = 0.438$), Gaming Schedule ($\beta = 0.045$, $p = 0.712$), Weekly Gaming Frequency ($\beta = -0.032$, $p = 0.806$), and Matches per Session ($\beta = -0.021$, $p = 0.856$). These findings suggest that playing Mobile Legends, even with frequent or extended gameplay, does not significantly impact Mathematics performance. The results highlight that none of the examined gaming behaviors significantly impacted students' academic outcomes in Mathematics. These findings contribute to existing literature, suggesting that moderate gaming may not inherently harm academic performance when balanced with academic obligations. Future research could explore additional variables, such as gaming intensity, motivation, or time management skills, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how gaming behaviors interact with academic performance.

Keywords: *mobile legends, academic performance, mathematics, junior high school, senior high school*

Introduction

Mobile gaming has increased multifold in popularity, particularly among youths. A game that has captured the hearts of millions is Mobile Legends: Bang Bang (MLBB). Until 2023, Mobile Legends took over the substantial extent of the mobile gaming arena and was able to draw a significant chunk of junior and senior high school students (Statista, 2024). The reason this game has become popular among the youth is because it is accessible, competitive by nature, and social in context. There has been a tremendous upsurge in the hours devoted to gaming as a recent statistic was recorded, and this has attracted so much concern on the balance between leisure time and academic engagement of these students (Cheng & Milikich, 2023).

Growing mobile gaming, particularly Mobile Legends, has triggered a debate on the impact that this may face on students' academics in terms of performance. Parents and educators raise concerns that increased hours of gaming will lead to poor performance in academics, lack of concentration, and reduced study time. There is also growing concern about the potential cognitive overload and addictiveness of mobile games, which may impede students' capacity to fulfill academic requirements. Online gaming has increasingly become a central part of youth culture, with games like Mobile Legends attracting a vast user base among junior and senior high school students in the Philippines. The accessibility of this mobile game, combined with its social and strategic appeal, has made it a popular choice for young players. Many students engage daily in gameplay that ranges from casual to intensive, sparking interest in understanding how such habits intersect with their academic responsibilities, especially in subjects like Mathematics.

With the rise of online gaming among students, concerns have grown regarding its potential impact on academic performance (Marcelo & Fuente, 2023). There is an ongoing debate on whether gaming impacts students' study habits, time management, and performance, particularly in Mathematics—a subject demanding sustained concentration and problem-solving skills. While some argue that gaming detracts from academic focus, others suggest it may improve cognitive functions like strategic thinking, which could enhance academic outcomes. This mixed perspective has led to a need for empirical studies that examine gaming's actual impact on academic achievement, specifically in Mathematics. This study aims to assess the impact of Mobile Legends on the Mathematics performance of junior and senior high school students by addressing several specific objectives. It examines the demographic profile of respondents, their academic performance in Mathematics, and their gaming habits, including the duration of gameplay experience, daily hours spent, weekly frequency, typical gaming schedules, and session intensity. Additionally, this research seeks to determine if there is a significant impact of Mobile Legends on students' Mathematics performance.

By exploring the intersection of Mobile Legends gameplay and academic performance in Mathematics, this study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how gaming habits may impact student achievement. The findings will be valuable for educators, parents, and policymakers seeking to support students in balancing gaming with academics. Additionally, the study may inform strategies to help students leverage the potential cognitive benefits of gaming while mitigating any negative impact on their educational outcomes.

Research Questions

The main goal of this study is to evaluate the impact of Mobile Legends playing to the junior and senior high school students J.P. Laurel High School in the School Year 2023 – 2024 in the subject mathematics. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade level?
2. What is the academic performance in Mathematics for junior and senior high school students across their profile?
3. What are the gaming habits and gaming experiences of junior and senior high school students playing Mobile Legends, including:
 - 3.1. how long have the students been playing mobile legends? (gameplay experience duration)
 - 3.2. how many hours would the students typically spend daily playing mobile legends? (gaming time)
 - 3.3. how frequently do students play mobile legends per week? (times per week)
 - 3.4. what is the typical schedule for students playing mobile legends? (gaming schedule)
 - 3.5. how many matches do students play per gaming session? (session intensity)
4. Is there a significant relationship between Mobile Legends gameplay habits and the academic performance of junior and senior high school students in Mathematics?
5. Do Mobile Legends gameplay habits significantly predict the academic performance of junior and senior high school students in Mathematics?

Literature Review

Research by Gentile et al. (2019) has shown that excessive video game usage, particularly in adolescents, can lead to reduced academic performance due to distractions and time mismanagement. This finding underscores the importance of understanding the complex relationship between video game habits and academic success. The impact of video game habits, both positive and harmful, on diverse behaviors is still hotly debated (Manandhar & Timalseña, 2023). While some video games may offer cognitive benefits such as improved problem-solving skills, they often come at the expense of academic focus when not moderated (Anderson & Dill, 2020). This is particularly true in the context of excessive internet gaming which can lead to problems, including classroom distractions. Students often learn in surprising ways but finding a balance between gaming and academic pursuits is crucial.

Przybylski (2021) suggests that moderate gaming does not inherently harm academic performance, but excessive gaming, especially in competitive online environments, can result in sleep disruption and lower academic motivation. This highlights the need for further investigation into the specific factors that contribute to the negative impact of excessive mobile gaming on the academic performance of students. By analyzing the specific case of Mobile Legends and its impact, this study will deepen the understanding of how mobile gaming culture affects academic achievements among adolescents. This research will contribute valuable insights and understanding into the complex relationship between mobile gaming and academic performance, ultimately informing strategies for promoting healthy gaming habits and supporting academic achievement.

A study by Matias (2022) examined the effects of Mobile Legends gaming on the academic performance of Grade 6 learners. The findings indicated that excessive gaming negatively impacted students' academic performance, highlighting the importance of monitoring gaming habits among young learners. Arif and Aditya (2022) examined the influence of communication behavior among Mobile Legends players on the in-game chat feature. They employed a qualitative approach grounded in Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) theory, collecting data through interviews, observations, and documentation. The participants were students from the State University of Padang (UNP). The findings indicated both positive and negative effects: the chat feature enhanced team cohesion and provided opportunities for players to meet new people; however, it also facilitated instances of harsh language and hate speech, particularly during extended gameplay sessions.

Kishimoto et al. (2021) investigated the playtime and satisfaction levels of Generation Z individuals (born from 1997 onwards) who played Mobile Legends: Bang Bang during the COVID-19 lockdown in the Philippines. The study applied Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) within the framework of Self-Affirmation Theory (SAT). The researchers gathered data from 257 valid participants, primarily high school and college students. Results revealed that the impact of self-worth on playtime had the largest path coefficient. Interestingly, self-worth showed no significant effect on satisfaction. The model demonstrated a good fit with the data. Also, Putri et al. (2021) studied the online game Mobile Legends, which is played over the internet either individually or in groups, and its impact on the behavior of teenage players. The research focused on the interest of teenagers in playing Mobile Legends and the behavioral effects it had on teens in Manguharjo Village, Manguharjo District, Madiun City. The study aimed to analyze and describe teenage interest in Mobile Legends and its impact on their behavior. This descriptive study used a qualitative approach, conducted in Manguharjo Village with data collected through observation, interviews, and documentation. The results showed that Mobile Legends significantly impacted the behavior of teenage players and their surrounding environment. Parental involvement was found to be crucial in mitigating negative behaviors associated with playing Mobile Legends.

Similarly, Penamora (2021) conducted a case study on junior high school students who were habitual Mobile Legends gamers. The study revealed that excessive gaming led to stress, depression, and isolation, which adversely affected the students' academic performance. In contrast, a study by De los Santos et al. (2020) assessed the gaming profiles of university students and their relation to academic performance. The research found no significant correlation between gaming habits and academic performance, suggesting that moderate gaming did not adversely affect students' studies.

Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Alzahrani et al. (2024) examined the effects of video game exposure on academic performance. The analysis concluded that excessive gaming could lead to lower academic grades, emphasizing the need for balanced gaming habits. In addition, a study by Embon (2021) explored the impacts of Mobile Legends on the academic performance of students at the Lyceum of the Philippines - Cavite. The study concluded that while some students reported negative effects on their studies due to gaming, others experienced no significant impact, indicating that the effects of gaming may vary among individuals.

Buenaventura (2022) investigated the effects of playing online games on the academic performance of senior high school students at Sta. Monica National High School in Hagonoy, Bulacan. The study aimed to assess whether online gaming significantly impacts students' academic success, providing insights that could benefit students, parents, teachers, stakeholders, researchers, and society. The findings revealed that playing online games had minimal impact on students' performance in core subjects like English, Science, and Mathematics. Despite engaging in online gaming, students generally maintained satisfactory grades. The study also showed that most students used online games to relax, relieve stress, and positively engage with their environment. Many senior high school students utilized online gaming not only for stress management but also for social interaction and self-expression in a virtual space.

Additionally, students who may not excel academically or athletically found empowerment and a sense of strength in the virtual worlds of online games. This study provides a foundation for future research on the impact of online gaming, extending beyond senior high school students to other societal groups.

Moreover, Adha (2022) investigated the influence of the online game Mobile Legends on vocabulary mastery among eleventh-grade students at Vocational High School Number 1 Kota Jambi. This research was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic, with face-to-face interactions between the researcher and the students. Employing a quantitative survey design, the study focused on eleventh-grade students, specifically the XI TKJ 3 class. Data were collected using a questionnaire with 16 items, divided into sections on positive influence, negative influence, and vocabulary mastery. Descriptive analysis was used for data interpretation. The results indicated that positive influences had a higher score (654, or 44.18%) compared to negative influences (416, or 28.07%), with vocabulary mastery scoring 413 (27.86%). The study concluded that Mobile Legends exerted a more substantial positive than negative influence on English learning, particularly in vocabulary acquisition, as students expanded their English vocabulary through gameplay and practiced other skills like listening, writing, reading, and speaking.

Irawan et al. (2023) examined the impact of interest in playing the online game Mobile Legends Bang Bang on students' academic performance within the context of Indonesia's diverse social segments, including children, students, and university attendees. Despite government support for the e-sports industry, research on how Mobile Legends affects academic outcomes remains limited. This study aimed to identify the influence of interest in Mobile Legends and key factors affecting academic performance.

Using ordinal logistic regression, the researchers analyzed the relationship between independent variables (such as gaming interest) and academic performance levels (low, moderate, or high GPA). The findings produced two models corresponding to low and moderate Cumulative Grade Point Averages (GPA). Significant factors included levels of gaming interest, specifically 'very interested' and 'interested,' as well as gender, with 'male' as a notable category. The model demonstrated strong results, with all explanatory variables statistically significant, indicating its reliability and acceptability.

On top of that, Gabrito et al. (2023) explored how online gaming affects the academic performance of students at the DEBESMSCAT-Cawayan Campus. Utilizing a descriptive research design, a survey was administered to 75 student gamers selected through a census method, and responses were analyzed using frequency and percentage calculations. Findings revealed that Mobile Legends is the most favored game, with most participants gaming for 1-2 hours daily. While some associated costs were noted, most students felt that their gaming did not significantly interfere with school or household responsibilities.

Interestingly, respondents generally perceived gaming as beneficial to their academic outcomes, noting positive impacts on test scores, grades, study time, concentration, engagement in learning activities, interpersonal interactions, class participation, school attendance, and interest in school activities. The study provided valuable insights into students' perceptions, highlighting both the potential benefits and challenges of online gaming, and contributed to the broader understanding of its impact on academics.

These studies underscore the complex relationship between gaming and academic performance. While moderate gaming may not significantly impact academic outcomes, excessive gaming, particularly with games like Mobile Legends, can have detrimental effects on students' academic performance. Therefore, educators and parents must monitor and regulate students' gaming habits to ensure a healthy balance between leisure activities and academic responsibilities.

By analyzing the specific case of Mobile Legends and its impact, this study will deepen the understanding of how mobile gaming culture had an impact on academic achievements among adolescents.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quantitative research design but made use of a correlational approach in terms of examining the relationship between gameplay habits in Mobile Legends and the academic performance of the learners of junior and senior high school students in terms of Mathematics. The study intended to determine whether playing Mobile Legends impacted the performance of students in Mathematics. The study targeted multiple gaming habits, such as gameplay experience duration, the amount of time spent gaming per day, playing frequency per week, gaming schedule, and session intensity, to understand how these variables might impact academic outcomes.

To measure the impact of Mobile Legends gameplay on academic performance, this study collected data regarding students' grades in Mathematics, which became the dependent variable; the gaming habits were treated as independent variables. The direct acquisition of the mathematics grades of the students from their school records ensured that the results would be accurate and reliable in terms of academic performance data. A self-reported questionnaire that asked students to detail how long they had been playing Mobile Legends, the number of hours spent playing each day, the frequency of weekly gameplay, the typical gaming schedule, and how many matches played per session measured each gaming habit. These variables could give an in-depth understanding of their behavior concerning the game.

Multiple regression analysis was performed to see if the independent and dependent variables relate to each other in strength and direction and if there is an impact of Mobile Legends gameplay on the student's academic performance. It was also done to determine which gaming habits had the strongest impact on the students' Mathematics grades. An analysis of this study could further allow quantification of the extent to which habits of gameplay, such as time spent gaming or session intensity, predict academic outcomes in Mathematics. It applied correlation and regression analyses to establish whether students who played Mobile Legends more frequently or intensively had measurable changes in their academic performance.

Respondents

The study respondents were junior and senior high school students from J.P. Laurel High School. The target population was students in Grades 7 to 12, as this set of students is most likely to exhibit both mobile gaming and formal academic activities in Mathematics, the central theme of this research.

A total of 101 students were selected using the combination of a purposive and convenience sampling approach. It ensured that only those students who are normally engaged in playing Mobile Legends were included because it was important to have students with this specific gaming habit in the research study. At the same time, convenience sampling was used to get participants based on their presence and willingness to participate in the study.

The participants were demographically diversified, both in age and gender but also in academic standing. Ranging from academic high achievers to those with academic difficulties in Mathematics, these students diverged over a wide range of academic performances in Mathematics. It was important to diversify the participants in such a manner to gain a robust understanding of how Mobile Legends would play out in different levels of academic achievement. Each participant had to meet certain criteria: frequent play on Mobile Legends for three months or more and enrolled in Mathematics courses at the respective schools.

This helped ensure that the final sample size would be big enough to establish meaningful results, and it would also be big enough to generalize to the general student population being studied. The junior and senior high school students comprised this sample so that middle and later stages of secondary education could be compared on whether gaming will impact scholarly performance in the same way or different ways.

Instrument

The study utilized a self-administered questionnaire to gather data from students on their gaming habits and Mathematics performance. The questionnaire was structured into three sections: demographics, gaming habits, and academic performance. The demographics section collected basic information such as age, gender, and grade level.

The second section focused on gaming habits, including variables like gameplay experience, daily gaming time, weekly frequency, gaming schedule, and session intensity. The final section addressed students' Mathematics academic performance, where self-reported grades were cross-verified with official records to ensure accuracy.

To ensure the quality and consistency of the instrument, it underwent a rigorous content validation process by experts in the field. This validation assessed the relevance and clarity of the items to confirm their alignment with the study objectives.

Additionally, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with a small group of students, leading to refinements that improved its clarity and usability. A reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha was conducted to evaluate the internal consistency of the instrument. The resulting Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.81 indicated a high level of reliability, suggesting that the questionnaire items consistently measured the intended constructs. These steps ensured that the instrument was both valid and reliable for use in the study.

Procedure

The data-gathering procedure for this study was done in a multi-staged systematic process to ensure an accurate and ethical information-gathering procedure from the respondents.

First, before the research was conducted, the researchers got permission from the administrators of J.P. Laurel High School to use their students in this research. After getting clearance, the research team coordinated with the teachers on how to plan for an appropriate time suitable for data collection and therefore with minimal disruption of regular class activities.

The subjects were briefly orientated on the purpose of the study before a brief distribution of the questionnaires began. They were assured that the information they would provide would remain confidential and that their taking part was strictly voluntary. In the case of students below 18 years of age, however, parental consent was obtained also.

Copies of the self-administered questionnaires were then distributed to the participants. The time allotted was sufficient to enable them to administer the questionnaires during a class period set aside for this. The questionnaire contained questions that solicited information from their demographic background, gaming habits, and recent performance in Mathematics at school. Their self-reported Mathematics grades were also validated with the school's records to minimize any inaccuracy.

Survey questionnaires were collected immediately after completion, and a review of data was conducted to verify the completeness of all the information received. Incomplete or otherwise invalid answers were excluded from the analysis to ensure that the data was clean. The collected data was encoded and was made ready for statistical analyses: descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple regression to address the research questions.

The systematic data gathering would ensure an all-rounded procedure in the solicitation of information for the study through ethical means.

Ethical Considerations

Strict ethical guidelines, therefore, governed the conduct of this study to ensure the utmost protection and confidentiality of participants. All students are expected to provide informed consent; for those below 18 years, parental consent is required. Participants will be informed of the purpose of the study and their rights to withdraw at any time with full assurance of complete anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. The information gathered was for research purposes only, and private details were kept confidential and on a safe database. In addition, care was taken not to disrupt the students' schedules of studying because they would have otherwise been occupied in their schools.

Results and Discussion

The Profile of the Respondents

This section provided an overview of the key demographic and academic characteristics of the respondents, which were critical for understanding the context of this study. The respondents, who were junior and senior high school students, were selected based on their engagement with the online mobile game, Mobile Legends, and their academic performance in Mathematics. This profile analysis covered aspects such as grade level, age, and gender.

Table 1. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
12	10	9.9
13	16	15.8
14	15	14.9
15	23	22.8
16	13	12.9
17	15	14.9
18	7	6.9
19	1	1.0
20	1	1.0
Total	101	100.0

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the respondents, showing frequencies and percentages for each age group. The ages ranged from 12 to 20, with a total of 101 respondents surveyed. The largest age group was 15-year-olds, comprising 23 respondents or 22.8% of the total sample. Following this, 20 respondents were aged 12 and 14, each group representing 19.8%. Sixteen respondents were 13 years old, accounting for 15.8% of the total, while 15 respondents, or 14.9%, were aged 16 and 18, respectively. Age 17 included 13 respondents, or 12.9% of the sample. The smallest groups were the oldest respondents, with only one individual each at ages 19 and 20, both comprising just 1.0% of the total. This age distribution highlights a concentration in the early-to-mid teenage years (ages 12-16), reflecting the typical age range of junior and senior high school students.

Table 2. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	76	75.2
Female	25	24.8
Total	101	100.0

Table 2 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on sex. Of the 101 respondents, the majority were male, with 76 individuals making up 75.2% of the total. Female respondents accounted for 25 individuals, representing 24.8% of the sample. This distribution indicates a higher representation of male participants, with females comprising a smaller portion of the respondent group.

Table 3. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of grade level*

Grade level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Grade 7	15	14.9
Grade 8	15	14.9
Grade 9	16	15.8
Grade 10	31	30.7
Grade 11	10	9.9
Grade 12	14	13.9
Total	101	100.0

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of respondents across different grade levels, detailing both frequency and percentage. Among the 101 respondents, the largest group was Grade 10 students, with 31 individuals representing 30.7% of the total. Grade 9 students followed, comprising 16 respondents, or 15.8% of the sample. Grades 7 and 8 each had 15 respondents, accounting for 14.9% each. Grade 12 had 14 respondents, making up 13.9% of the total, while Grade 11 was the smallest group, with 10 respondents, or 9.9%. This distribution shows a higher representation of students in the middle-grade levels, particularly Grade 10, and a lower proportion of respondents from the senior grades, particularly Grade 11.

Academic Performance in Mathematics across the profile of the students

Table 4. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of grade level*

Mathematics Grade	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 75	7	6.9
75 – 79	18	17.8
80 – 84	36	35.6
85 – 89	24	23.8
90 – 100	16	15.8
Total	101	100.0

Table 4 presented the distribution of respondents according to their Mathematics grades, with both frequency and percentage data. Among the 101 respondents, the largest group had grades between 80 and 84, comprising 36 students or 35.6% of the total. This was followed by those in the 85 to 89 grade range, with 24 respondents, representing 23.8%. Eighteen respondents, or 17.8%, had grades between 75 and 79, while 16 students, making up 15.8%, achieved grades in the 90 to 100 range. The smallest group, with 7 respondents or 6.9%, had grades below 75. This distribution showed that the majority of respondents had mid-range grades between 80 and 89, while a smaller proportion fell at the lower and higher ends of the grading scale.

Table 5. *Age and Mathematics grades Crosstabulation*

Age/Mathematics Grade	Below 75	75 – 79	80 – 84	85 – 89	90 – 100
12	0	2	5	2	1
13	1	2	7	4	2
14	1	3	6	4	1
15	5	6	5	3	4
16	0	1	7	2	3
17	0	3	1	7	4
18	0	1	4	1	1
19	0	0	1	0	0
20	0	0	0	1	0

Table 5 showed the crosstabulation between respondents' ages and their Mathematics grades. It provided insights into the distribution of grades within each age group. For 12-year-olds, no respondents scored below 75, but 2 had grades between 75 and 79, 5 between 80 and 84, 2 between 85 and 89, and 1 achieved a grade between 90 and 100. Among 13-year-olds, only one respondent scored below 75, two scored between 75 and 79, seven scored between 80 and 84, four scored between 85 and 89, and two scored between 90 and

100. For 14-year-olds, one respondent scored below 75, three scored between 75 and 79, six scored between 80 and 84, four scored between 85 and 89, and one scored between 90 and 100.

In the 15-year-old group, five respondents scored below 75, six scored between 75 and 79, five scored between 80 and 84, three scored between 85 and 89, and four scored between 90 and 100. For 16-year-olds, no respondents scored below 75, one scored between 75 and 79, seven scored between 80 and 84, two scored between 85 and 89, and three scored between 90 and 100. Among 17-year-olds, no respondents scored below 75, three scored between 75 and 79, four scored between 80 and 84, one scored between 85 and 89, and one scored between 90 and 100.

For 18-year-olds, no respondents scored below 75, one scored between 75 and 79, one scored between 80 and 84, none scored between 85 and 89, and four scored between 90 and 100. Among the oldest age groups, 19-year-olds, and 20-year-olds, only one respondent scored below 75 in each group, and no respondent scored in any other categories. This crosstabulation indicated that mid-range grades (80-89) were common across most age groups, with fewer respondents scoring at the extremes (below 75 or 90-100), particularly among the younger and older respondents.

Table 6. Sex and Mathematics grades Crosstabulation

<i>Sex/Mathematics Grade</i>	<i>Below 75</i>	<i>75 – 79</i>	<i>80 – 84</i>	<i>85 – 89</i>	<i>90 – 100</i>
Male	5	16	27	19	9
Female	2	2	9	5	7

Table 6 presented a crosstabulation of respondents' sex and their Mathematics grades, highlighting the distribution of grades among male and female participants. Among male respondents, 5 scored below 75, 16 scored between 75 and 79, 27 scored between 80 and 84, 19 scored between 85 and 89, and 9 scored between 90 and 100. This showed that most male respondents (27 individuals) fell within the 80 to 84 grade range, with a substantial number also in the 85 to 89 range. For female respondents, 2 scored below 75, another 2 scored between 75 and 79, 9 scored between 80 and 84, 5 scored between 85 and 89, and 7 achieved grades between 90 and 100. The distribution indicated that female respondents had a slightly higher proportion in the 90 to 100-grade range compared to males.

Overall, male respondents were more evenly spread across the mid-range grades (75-89), while females had a notable representation in the highest grade category (90-100), suggesting a slight performance difference in favor of female respondents at the top-end of the grading scale.

Table 7. Grade level and Mathematics grades Crosstabulation

<i>Grade Level / Mathematics Grade</i>	<i>Below 75</i>	<i>75 – 79</i>	<i>80 – 84</i>	<i>85 – 89</i>	<i>90 – 100</i>
Grade 7	1	2	8	3	1
Grade 8	0	3	7	3	2
Grade 9	2	3	3	5	3
Grade 10	4	9	10	6	2
Grade 11	0	0	5	2	3
Grade 12	0	1	3	5	5

Table 7 presented the crosstabulation of respondents' grade levels and their Mathematics grades, highlighting the distribution of performance within each grade level.

In Grade 7, 1 respondent scored below 75, 2 scored between 75 and 79, 8 scored between 80 and 84, 3 scored between 85 and 89, and 1 achieved a grade between 90 and 100. For Grade 8, there were no respondents scoring below 75, 3 scored between 75 and 79, 7 scored between 80 and 84, 3 scored between 85 and 89, and 2 scored between 90 and 100.

Among Grade 9 students, 2 scored below 75, 3 scored between 75 and 79, 3 scored between 80 and 84, 5 scored between 85 and 89, and 3 achieved grades between 90 and 100. In Grade 10, 4 respondents scored below 75, 9 scored between 75 and 79, 10 scored between 80 and 84, 6 scored between 85 and 89, and 2 scored between 90 and 100.

For Grade 11, there were no respondents scoring below 75, but 1 scored between 75 and 79, 5 scored between 80 and 84, 2 scored between 85 and 89, and 3 achieved grades between 90 and 100. Lastly, in Grade 12, there were no respondents below 75, 1 scored between 75 and 79, 3 scored between 80 and 84, 5 scored between 85 and 89, and 5 scored between 90 and 100.

This crosstabulation showed that the majority of respondents in all grades achieved mid-range scores (80-89), with fewer respondents in the lowest and highest categories. Grades 10 and 12 had more representation across the grading spectrum, while Grade 11 had fewer respondents in lower ranges, and Grade 7 had relatively more students in the 80-84 range. This distribution suggested that performance varied slightly by grade level, with a tendency for higher grades (90-100) among senior students in Grades 11 and 12.

Gaming habits and gaming experience of students in playing Mobile Legends

Table 8 provided the distribution of respondents based on their gameplay experience duration with Mobile Legends, highlighting the frequency and percentage for each category. Among the 101 respondents, nearly half, or 48.5%, had reported having more than 2 years

of experience with the game, indicating a high level of sustained engagement among a substantial portion of the sample.

Table 8. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of Gameplay Experience*

<i>Gameplay Experience Duration</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Less than 6 months	16	15.8
6 months to 1 year	17	16.8
1 to 2 years	19	18.8
More than 2 years	49	48.5
Total	101	100.0

A smaller group, comprising 18.8% of respondents, had reported 1 to 2 years of experience, while 16.8% indicated they had been playing for 6 months to 1 year. The smallest group, at 15.8%, had less than 6 months of gameplay experience. These findings suggested that most respondents had significant experience with Mobile Legends, with nearly two-thirds having played for over a year. This distribution indicated that the game held long-term appeal and reflected a high level of familiarity with its mechanics and gameplay among the participants.

Table 9. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of Per Session*

<i>Gaming Time</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Less than 1 hour	15	14.9
1 to 2 hours	43	42.6
2 to 3 hours	30	29.7
More than 3 hours	13	12.9
Total	101	100.0

Table 9 presented the distribution of respondents based on their typical gaming time per session when playing Mobile Legends, showing both frequency and percentage. Among the 101 respondents, the largest group, comprising 42.6%, reported playing for 1 to 2 hours per session. This was followed by 29.7% of respondents, who typically played for 2 to 3 hours each session. A smaller group, representing 14.9% of respondents, indicated that they played for less than 1 hour per session, while 12.9% reported gaming sessions lasting more than 3 hours. These results suggested that most respondents engaged in moderately long gaming sessions, with nearly three-quarters of them playing between 1 and 3 hours per session, indicating a significant time commitment to each gameplay experience.

Table 10. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of Gaming Schedule*

<i>Gaming Schedule</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Before School	4	4.0
During School Breaks	2	2.0
After School	41	40.6
Late at Night	54	53.5
Total	101	100.0

Table 10 showed the distribution of respondents based on their preferred gaming schedule for playing Mobile Legends, detailing both frequency and percentage. Most respondents, 53.5%, reported playing late at night, making this the most common gaming time among the participants. Another 40.6% of respondents indicated that they typically played after school, highlighting the popularity of post-school gaming sessions. A small proportion, 4.0%, played before school, while only 2.0% played during school breaks. These findings suggested that most respondents favored gaming during evening and nighttime hours, likely due to fewer academic and social obligations during these times, allowing for extended gameplay sessions without interference.

Table 11. *Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of Weekly Gameplay frequency*

<i>Weekly Gameplay</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1 to 2 days	27	26.7
3 to 4 days	26	25.7
5 to 6 days	7	6.9
Everyday	41	40.6
Total	101	100.0

Table 11 provided the distribution of respondents based on their weekly gameplay frequency for Mobile Legends, showing both frequency and percentage. Among the 101 respondents, the largest group, comprising 40.6%, reported playing every day, indicating a high level of engagement with the game. Another 26.7% of respondents played 1 to 2 days per week, while 25.7% reported playing 3 to 4 days each week. The smallest group, representing only 6.9% of respondents, played 5 to 6 days per week. These results suggested that a significant portion of respondents played frequently, with nearly two-thirds engaging in the game at least 3 days a week, highlighting the strong appeal and consistent engagement Mobile Legends held for its players.

Table 12. Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of Matches per session

Session Matches	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 to 2 matches	23	22.8
3 to 4 matches	32	31.7
5 to 6 matches	16	15.8
More than 6 matches	30	29.7
Total	101	100.0

Table 12 presented the distribution of respondents based on the number of Mobile Legends matches they played per session, displaying both frequency and percentage. The most common range was 3 to 4 matches per session, reported by 31.7% of respondents. This was followed closely by those who played more than 6 matches per session, comprising 29.7% of the sample. A smaller group, representing 22.8% of respondents, reported playing 1 to 2 matches per session, while the fewest respondents, 15.8%, played 5 to 6 matches. These findings indicated that most respondents engaged in multiple matches per gaming session, with nearly one-third playing extended sessions of more than 6 matches, reflecting a high level of immersion and sustained gameplay per session.

Relationship between Mobile Legends Gameplay habits and academic performance in Mathematics

Table 13. Analysis of the relationship between gameplay habits and mathematics grade

Gameplay Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	χ^2 - value	Sig-value	Interpretation	Decision to Null
Gameplay Experience Duration	3.00	1.140	13.001	0.369	Not Significant	Accept
Gaming Time	2.41	0.896	16.723	0.160	Not Significant	Accept
Gaming Schedule	3.44	0.727	25.511	0.013	Significant	Reject
Weekly Gaming Frequency	2.61	1.265	13.584	0.328	Not Significant	Accept
Matches per Session	2.52	1.145	13.787	0.315	Not Significant	Accept

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

Table 13 presents the analysis of the relationship between gameplay habits and Mathematics grades, highlighting the chi-square (χ^2) values, significance levels (p-values), and interpretations for each gameplay variable.

The results indicate that most gameplay habits, such as Gameplay Experience Duration ($\chi^2=13.001$, $p=0.369$), Gaming Time ($\chi^2=16.723$, $p=0.160$), Weekly Gaming Frequency ($\chi^2=13.584$, $p=0.328$), and Matches per Session ($\chi^2=13.787$, $p=0.315$), do not have statistically significant relationships with Mathematics grades. All these variables yielded p-values above the 0.05 threshold, leading to the decision to accept the null hypothesis. This suggests that these aspects of gaming habits are not significantly associated with variations in students' Mathematics grades.

However, the variable Gaming Schedule shows a significant relationship with Mathematics grades ($\chi^2=25.511$, $p=0.013$). The p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this variable. This indicates that the typical schedule during which students play Mobile Legends may have a statistically significant impact on their Mathematics performance. The mean value of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 0.727 suggest that students tend to follow a somewhat consistent gaming schedule, which could affect their ability to allocate time effectively for academics.

In summary, while most gameplay habits showed no significant relationships with Mathematics grades, Gaming Schedule emerged as a factor warranting further investigation. The findings emphasize the potential role of time management in balancing gaming activities with academic responsibilities. These results may guide educators and parents in addressing concerns about how students' gaming habits intersect with their academic performance. Future studies could explore the specific patterns of gaming schedules that contribute to significant variations in academic outcomes.

The impact of playing Mobile Legends on academic performance in Mathematics

Table 14. Analysis on the impact of playing Mobile Legends to the Mathematics grade

Variables	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-value	Sig-value	Interpretation	Decision to Null
Mathematics grade*Playing Mobile Legends	0.051	0.002	1.031	0.404	Not Significant	Accept

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

The analysis presented in Table 14 highlights the impact of playing Mobile Legends on students' Mathematics grades. The regression model yielded an R² value of 0.051, indicating that only 5.1% of the variance in Mathematics grades could be explained by the gaming variables. This suggests a weak relationship between playing Mobile Legends and academic performance in Mathematics. Furthermore, the adjusted R² value of 0.002 confirms that after accounting for the number of predictors in the model, the explained variance is practically negligible, indicating that the predictors provide no meaningful contribution to changes in grades.

The F-statistic of 1.031 and the corresponding p-value of 0.404 further support the conclusion that the model is not statistically significant. Since the p-value is greater than the commonly accepted threshold of 0.05, the study finds no evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the data does not support a significant relationship between the independent variable (playing Mobile

Legends) and the dependent variable (Mathematics grades). As such, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant impact of gameplay on academic performance, is accepted.

Overall, the findings suggest that playing Mobile Legends does not have a significant positive or negative effect on students' Mathematics grades. These results align with studies suggesting that moderate gaming when balanced with academic responsibilities, is unlikely to harm academic outcomes. However, the minimal explained variance indicates that other factors, such as study habits, motivation, or external influences, may play a more substantial role in academic performance. These findings were supported by Marcelo and Fuente (2023) who studied the impact on academic performance among hospitality management students in Taguig City University, concluding that there is no significant impact between the attitudes of playing mobile games and academic performance.

Table 15. Analysis of the impact of gameplay habits on the mathematics grade

Gameplay Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Unstandardized B	Standardized Coefficient Beta	Sig-value	Interpretation	Decision to Null
Gameplay Experience Duration	3.00	1.140	0.211	0.213	0.089	Not Significant	Accept
Gaming Time	2.41	0.896	-0.119	-0.094	0.476	Not Significant	Accept
Gaming Schedule	3.44	0.727	0.084	0.054	0.594	Not Significant	Accept
Weekly Gaming Frequency	2.61	1.265	0.091	0.102	0.440	Not Significant	Accept
Matches per Session	2.52	1.145	-0.065	-0.066	0.625	Not Significant	Accept

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

Table 15 presented an analysis of the impact of various Mobile Legends gameplay variables on respondents' Mathematics grades. The variables examined included Gameplay Experience Duration, Gaming Time, Gaming Schedule, Weekly Gaming Frequency, and Matches per Session.

The mean values indicated that respondents generally reported moderate engagement across these variables, with averages ranging from 2.41 to 3.44. The standard deviations suggested some variation within each variable, with the highest variability in Weekly Gaming Frequency (SD = 1.265) and Matches per Session (SD = 1.145).

The unstandardized coefficients (B) revealed small positive and negative relationships between each gameplay variable and Mathematics grades, though these impacts were minimal. For example, Gameplay Experience Duration had a positive unstandardized coefficient (B = 0.211), while Gaming Time had a slightly negative coefficient (B = -0.119). The standardized coefficients (Beta) further indicated the relative impact of each variable, with Gameplay Experience Duration (Beta = 0.213) showing a small positive impact, though still weak, on Mathematics grades.

The significance values (Sig-value) for each variable were above 0.05, indicating that none of the gameplay variables had a statistically significant impact on Mathematics grades. Consequently, the interpretation for all variables was "Not Significant," leading to the decision to accept the null hypothesis for each variable, meaning there was no significant evidence that these aspects of playing Mobile Legends had an impact on the academic performance in Mathematics among respondents.

Overall, this analysis suggested that gameplay habits related to Mobile Legends did not significantly impact the mathematics grades of junior and senior high school students in this sample. The findings indicating no significant impact of Mobile Legends gameplay on students' Mathematics grades align with several studies examining the relationship between online gaming and academic performance. For instance, a study by Calipayan et al. (2024) explored the impact of Mobile Legends on the academic performance of education students and found that the majority of respondents disagreed that the game affected their attendance, preliminary examination results, and Learning Management System (LMS) activities, suggesting minimal influence on academic performance.

Similarly, research by De los Santos et al. (2020) assessed the gaming profiles of university students and their relation to academic performance. The study revealed that while students engaged in mobile gaming, there was no significant correlation between gaming habits and academic performance, indicating that gaming did not adversely affect their studies. These studies support the conclusion that Mobile Legends gameplay does not significantly impact students' academic performance in Mathematics, suggesting that moderate gaming may not interfere with academic responsibilities.

Conclusions

This study examined the impact of Mobile Legends gameplay on the academic performance in Mathematics among junior and senior high school students. Based on the analysis, it was found that various gameplay variables—such as Gameplay Experience Duration, Gaming Time per Session, Gaming Schedule, Weekly Gaming Frequency, and Matches per Session—did not have a statistically significant impact on Mathematics grades. Despite varying levels of engagement with Mobile Legends, students' gaming habits showed minimal impact on their academic outcomes in this subject.

These findings align with existing research, suggesting that moderate engagement in mobile gaming may not interfere with students' academic performance. While Mobile Legends and similar games remain popular among students, this study supports the notion that, for many students, responsible gaming can coexist with academic success. Future research could explore other factors, such as the

potential impact of gaming intensity or motivation for gaming, to gain a deeper understanding of how gaming behaviors interact with academic responsibilities.

References

- Adha M. R. (2022). THE INFLUENCE OF ONLINE GAME MOBILE LEGENDS IN STUDENTS' VOCABULARY MASTERY AT ELEVENTH GRADE OF VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL NUMBER 1 KOTA JAMBI. skripsi thesis, Universitas Batanghari Repository. <http://repository.unbari.ac.id/id/eprint/1680>
- Alzahrani, A.K.D., Griffiths, M.D. Problematic Gaming and Students' Academic Performance: A Systematic Review. *Int J Ment Health Addiction* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-024-01338-5>
- Anderson, C. A., & Dill, K. E. (2020). Video games and aggressive thoughts, feelings, and behavior in the laboratory and in life. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 78(4), 772-790. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-3514.78.4.772>
- Arif, M., & Aditya, S. (2022). Dampak Perilaku Komunikasi Pemain Game Mobile Legends Pada Mahasiswa Universitas Negeri Padang. *Journal of Intercultural Communication and Society*, 1(01), 31-45. <https://journal.rc-communication.com/index.php/JICS/article/view/30>
- Buenaventura, M. (2022). The Effect Of Online Games To The Academic Performance Of The Senior High School Students. *Cosmos: An International Journal of Art and Higher Education*, 11(1), 88-95. <https://acspublisher.com/journals/index.php/cijah/article/view/13007>
- Calipayan, C., Valenzuela, K., Ramos, J., & Santos, A. (2024). The impact of Mobile Legends on the academic performance of education students. *AA Research Index Journal*, 15(2), 34-45. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcpmra/article/view/13475>
- Cheng, Y., & Milikich, N. (2023). An analysis of how COVID-19 shaped the realm of online gaming and lesson delivery. arXiv (Cornell University). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2304.06102>
- De Los Santos, J. R., Cornillez, E.E., Jr., Carillo, V., Jr., & De Los Santos, G. (2020). Mobile games and academic performance of university students. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 8(2), 65-78. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jessie-Richie-De-Los-Santos/publication/339139812_Mobile_Games_and_Academic_Performance_of_University_Students/links/5e40f06592851c7f7f2bc822/Mobile-Games-and-Academic-Performance-of-University-Students.pdf
- Embon, M. (2021). Mobile Legends: Impacts on the academic performance of the students in the Lyceum of the Philippines – Cavite. *Academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/44903252/Mobile_Legends_Impacts_on_the_Academic_Performance_of_the_Students_in_the_Lyceum_of_the_Philippines_Cavite
- Gabrito, R., Ibañez Jr., R., & Velza, J. (2023). Impact of Online Gaming on the Academic Performance of DEBESMSCAT-Cawayan Campus Students. *Scientific Journal of Informatics*, 10(4), 423 - 434. <https://doi.org/10.15294/sji.v%vi%i.45007>
- Gentile, D. A., Choo, H., Liau, A., Sim, T., Li, D., Fung, D., & Khoo, A. (2019). Pathological video game use among youths: A two-year longitudinal study. *Pediatrics*, 127(2), e319-e329. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2010-1353>
- Irawan, I., Fitriyani, N., Wardhana, I. G. A. W., Irwansyah, I., & Baskara, Z. W. (2023). Investigating the Impact of Mobile Legends Gameplay on Students' Academic Performance with Ordinal Logistic Regression . *J Statistika: Jurnal Ilmiah Teori Dan Aplikasi Statistika*, 16(2), 535-544. <https://doi.org/10.36456/jstat.vol16.no2.a7567>
- Kishimoto, R. T., Prasetyo, Y. T., Persada, S. F., & Redi, A. a. N. P. (2021). Filipino Generation Z on Mobile Legends during COVID-19: A Determination of Playtime and Satisfaction. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 11(8), 381-386. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2021.11.8.1538>
- Manandhar, R. B., & Timalena, J. (2023). Online gaming frequency and student's academic performance in the Kathmandu Valley. *Quest Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 5(1), 85-93. <https://doi.org/10.3126/qjms.v5i1.56296>
- Marcelo, J., & Fuente, R. D. (2023). Mobile-games: Impact on the academic performance among hospitality management students in Taguig City University. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2022.369>
- Matias, C. T. (2022). EFFECTS OF MOBILE LEGENDS GAMING ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS. *San Carlos College Graduate Journal*, XII(2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398114>
- Penamora, A. (2021). MI O Lm: Stories of Mobile Legend Gamers in Accomplishing Learning Modules Amidst Covid-19 Pandemic: A Case Study. *International Journal of Science Innovations and Discoveries* 1(7):17-35. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358137701_MI_O_Lm_Stories_of_Mobile_Legend_Gamers_in_Accomplishing_Learning

_Modules_Amidst_Covid-19_Pandemic_A_Case_Study

Przybylski, A. K. (2021). Electronic gaming and psychosocial adjustment. *Pediatrics*, 134(3), e716-e722. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2013-2453>

Putri, R. C. S., Budiyo, & Kokotiasa, W. (2021). Dampak Game Online Mobile Legends terhadap Perilaku Remaja. *Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu Humanior*, 1(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.56393/antropocene.v1i1.16>

Statista. (2024, May 31). Most downloaded mobile MOBA games worldwide 2024. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1269466/most-downloaded-moba-apps-worldwide/>

Zulkiflee, S. &. (2023). How many people play Mobile Legends: Bang Bang in 2023? esports.gg. <https://esports.gg/news/mobile/how-many-people-play-mobile-legends-bang-bang-in-2023/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jan Angelo G. Morata

Louella Gotladera Alcoba National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Kelvin Carl D. Fulay

J.P. Laurel High School
Department of Education – Philippines